

Navigating Maternity Leave: The Consequences of Leave Decision-Making on Wages in the United Kingdom

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Abstract:

This paper examines the effect of taking maternity leave and the maternity leave length on women's labour income in the United Kingdom (UK) using data from Understanding Society. I employ OLS and instrumental variable regression to explore the relationship between taking maternity leave and monthly wages. I find a negative causal effect of the length of leave on wages, with a 15.6% average motherhood wage penalty when the most observed leave is taken. Furthermore, I observe that longer leave periods are associated with greater wage penalties, as an additional week of maternity leave reduces wages by 0.3% on average. These findings have important implications for UK policies aimed at reducing gender inequality in the labour market and suggest further policy reform is necessary due to the negligible impact of Shared Parental Leave.

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1. Introduction

Becoming a mother is a transformative event, and the leave-taking decision a pivotal one that shapes the experience of motherhood for many. Maternity leave is a crucial component of several government policies and was designed to provide women with the time and resources necessary to care for their newborn child whilst retaining their employment. Nevertheless, there is a growing body of research indicating that taking maternity leave can have a significant negative impact on women's labour market outcomes, in particular, labour market participation and wages (Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017; Stearns, 2018; Kleven, 2019a; Andrew et al., 2021; Del Rey, Kyriacou and Silva, 2021). Persistent wage losses from motherhood, the motherhood wage penalty, are evident across many developed countries, with maternity leave policies being viewed as accentuating the gender pay gap and reinforcing the traditional gender division of labour. For example, Waldfogel (1998) shows that the motherhood wage penalty is 20% in Britain.

Gender inequality remains a pressing issue globally, and within the UK addressing this issue is crucial for policymakers to prevent further accentuation of the gender pay gap, with women earning approximately 8.3% less than men on average and being underrepresented in leadership positions (ONS, 2022). The motherhood wage penalty raises important questions about the impact of maternity leave policies on gender inequality. If a woman's labour income is being adversely affected by the decision to take leave and there is a negative causal effect of the length of leave taken on the mother's monthly wage, these findings are of importance to policymakers as they counteract the aims of such policies and offset the desired benefits. Furthermore, the low pay rates provided by the UK Statutory Maternity Policy and the strict eligibility criteria result in 28% of women not having access to paid maternity leave (Women's Budget Group, 2018; Chzhen, Gromada and Rees, 2019). The impact: in addition to Statutory Maternity Leave, employers are providing private maternity leave policies. Thus, the findings of this paper are also of interest to UK employers.

The interesting research question is whether taking maternity leave and the length of leave taken causes the motherhood wage penalty in the UK, thus contributing to gender inequality. To answer this question, I use Understanding Society data from 2009-2020 to determine whether there exists a statistically significant negative causal effect of taking maternity leave and the maternity leave length on labour income in the UK. To

do so, I regress wages on these variables of interest and control for time trends and observed characteristics that affect both wages and the leave-taking decision. I do this using an OLS regression, with the results suggesting that taking maternity leave is associated with an average monthly wage reduction of 15.8% and that taking an additional week of leave is associated with an average monthly wage reduction of 0.2%. However, these results are likely biased because the decision regarding maternity leave uptake and its length is endogenous due to unobservable factors affecting both the leave-taking decision and work circumstances, such as career aspirations or the opportunity cost of having children, which leads to omitted variable bias. Therefore, I instrument maternity leave length with the average maternity leave length within an occupation. The results support a negative causal effect between the length of maternity leave and monthly wages, showing that an additional week of leave increases the motherhood wage penalty by 0.3% on average.

This paper makes important contributions to the existing literature. Firstly, despite the unattractive Statutory Maternity Pay and variation in employer maternity leave policies, research focused on the UK is scant. The lack of comprehensive and accurate data on maternity leave uptake in the UK is likely a contributing factor to the limited attention given to maternity leave policies. In contrast to other countries, such as the Nordic countries, the UK does not prioritize work-family balance and gender equality to the same extent (Women's Budget Group, 2018). This poses the question of whether the effects of maternity leave policies on labour market outcomes found in other countries are generalisable to the UK. Secondly, the few studies that do focus on UK maternity leave rarely consider its length, which is pivotal in differentiating between short- and long-run effects on the labour market and important when considering the optimal leave length of policies. Thirdly, very little is known about heterogeneity in the leave decision, which I explore through differing education levels of mothers.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides background on maternity leave policies in the UK. Section 3 presents a summary of relevant literature. The dataset, along with sample selection decisions and summary statistics, are introduced in Section 4. Section 5 presents the empirical methodology. Section 6 presents the findings and robustness checks. Section 7 provides concluding remarks.

2. Background:

Statutory Maternity Leave (SML) in the UK is relatively long by European standards, with mothers able to take up to 52 weeks out of employment, made up of Ordinary Maternity Leave for the first 26 weeks and Additional Maternity Leave for the remaining. Despite this being largely preference-driven and the length of leave taken varying greatly over the population, a minimum of 2 weeks must be taken after childbirth. Statutory Maternity Pay (SMP) is paid for up to 39 weeks, comprising 90% of your average weekly earnings for the first 6 weeks and the lowest of £156.66 or 90% of your average weekly earnings for the next 33 weeks, with no pay for the remaining (UK Government, 2022). SML is a day-one right, whereas SMP is dependent on qualifying factors, where eligibility is based on employment status, a weekly earnings threshold and the length of current employment (Women's Budget Group, 2018). Even though it is ranked highly in its generosity of maternity leave length, the UK maternity pay rates are among the lowest in Europe, with the average payment rate for mothers at 31.3% of average national earnings, compared to Germany at 73.4% (Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017). Thus, creating pressure on UK employers to offer individual maternity leave policies known as Occupational Maternity Pay (OMP).

3.Literature Review:

There are extensive studies on the maternity leave decision in other disciplines, particularly psychology, which explore social norms and environmental factors that shape the perceptions of work and family commitment priorities (Morgenroth and Heilman, 2017; Hideg et al., 2018; Cukrowska-Torzewska and Matysiak, 2020). However, I will focus on economic literature, as this is primarily data-driven and has a greater emphasis on the effects of maternity leave on labour market outcomes.

3.1 Determinants of Length of Leave

The international literature has investigated the following determinants of the maternity leave length and the timing of a mother's return to work: leave policies and labour market conditions, childcare availability and subsidies, women's productivity in the labour market, pre-delivery job match quality, and the country-specific tax and benefit system (Gustafsson et al., 1996; Arntz, Dlygosz and Wilke, 2017). The negative wage penalty is typically at the forefront of the decision-making process, but childcare availability and price are becoming increasingly important factors once leave entitlements have expired (Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017). The literature primarily

focuses on return to work, career progression, occupational gender segregation, and wages as the main labour market outcomes affected by child-related leave. Maternity leave policies aim to effectively enable mothers to remain attached to the labour market while creating a work-life balance. The impact of such policies varies considerably by country and by study, with cross-country studies arguably overestimating the beneficial impact of maternity leave due to exogenous shocks in the labour market, whilst micro-level studies tend to underestimate the impact as they usually fail to consider broader social forces (Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017).

3.2 Gender Inequality and Female Participation Rates:

Maternity leave policies can be viewed as accentuating gender inequality because, despite supporting women's integration back into the labour market, they typically reinforce the traditional gender division of labour, emphasising the 'male breadwinner' model observed in many developed countries. Kleven (2019a) highlights the importance of motherhood for gender pay gaps and finds that a large proportion of aggregate gender inequality is due to having children. This can be explained by the occupational segregation that occurs after childbirth, with women falling behind men in occupational rank and the probability of maintaining higher managerial roles due to the lowering of employment continuity and loss of work experience (Ruhm, 1998; Mandel and Semyonov, 2006; Stearns, 2018; Kleven, 2019b). Also, studies find there is strong differentiation of career paths after childbirth, with many women reducing hours worked to become part-time or changing career paths to a more 'mother-friendly' occupation that offers greater flexibility in work hours (Gangl and Ziefle, 2009; Arntz, Dlygosz and Wilke, 2017). Another explanation for low female participation rates in the labour market, with Andrew et al. (2021) showing that the employment of women decreases from above 90% to 75% around childbirth, is the non-wage costs to employers. Positions that require training periods and qualifications make it expensive to fill the job gaps that occur when maternity leave is taken, which discourages employers from offering these roles to women and results in fewer women being hired (Mandel and Semyonov, 2006; Schonberg and Ludsteck, 2014). Gustafsson et al. (1996) suggest that there is no difference in labour market participation after one child, with the impact only occurring after the second or third birth. Whereas Akgunduz and Plantenga (2013) find that paid maternity leave decreases participation in the first year after birth regardless of the number of previous children. A further differentiating factor

for female participation is education, as Cipollone, Patacchini and Vallanti (2014) find that the participation of medium and highly educated women is more responsive to family-orientated policies. On the other hand, studies have found that maternity leave policies have led to an increase in female employment and higher rates of return to work (Ruhm, 1998; Mandel and Semyonov, 2006; Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017; Del Rey, Kyriacou and Silva, 2021). Job-protection leave policies such as the UK SML policy increase job-specific and firm-specific capital that eliminates future search costs and promotes re-entry to the labour market (Ruhm, 1998; Akgunduz and Plantenga, 2013). Furthermore, maternity leave policies provide women with better opportunities to join the labour force and enhance economic independence, which could lead to a reduction in gender inequality (Mandel and Semyonov, 2006). Many studies hint that these positive effects of maternity leave on female participation could be surpassed by its impact on wages and career opportunities. Overall, there is no clear consensus on the impact of maternity leave policies on female employment in current research, with many conflicting factors being considered.

3.3 Wages and the Gender Pay Gap:

The magnitude of the wage penalty resulting from time out of work due to childbirth has been extensively researched in the literature. Many studies conclude that maternity leave has a negative impact on mothers' relative wages across all countries (Ruhm, 1998; Aisenbrey, Evertsson and Grunow, 2009; Gangl and Zieflel, 2009; Akgunduz and Plantenga, 2013; Arntz, Dlugosz and Wilke, 2017; Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017; Stearns, 2018; Women's Budget Group, 2018; Kleven, 2019a; Del Rey, Kyriacou and Silva, 2021). Persistent wage losses from motherhood are largely driven by the depreciation of human capital that decreases the marginal product of labour during child-related career breaks (Aisenbrey, Evertsson and Grunow, 2009; Gangl and Zieflel, 2009; Blau and Kahn, 2017). As mentioned above, these career breaks can encourage a part-time return to work, which will reduce working hours and therefore labour incomes (Arntz, Dlygosz and Wilke, 2017). Gangl and Ziefel (2009), using British, US, and German data, show that the motherhood wage penalty is between 9% and 18% per child, with work interruptions and subsequent mobility accounting fully for these wage losses, which demonstrates that motherhood is a critical event behind the gender wage gap. This decrease in female relative wages is argued to be dependent on the wage elasticities of labour demand and supply, and the negative impact could be

mitigated if labour market experience and labour market attachment are highly valued in society (Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017). Waldfogel (1998) found that in Britain the motherhood wage penalty is 20%, where mothers of childbearing age earn 64% of men's pay while non-mothers earn 84%, highlighting the link between childbirth and the gender pay gap. Waldfogel (1998) also found that women who had maternity leave coverage and returned to work after childbirth received a wage premium that offset the negative wage effects. Schonberg and Ludsteck (2014) support this view and argue that these leave policies increase women's earnings as they allow mothers to retain valuable firm- and match-specific search capital after childbirth, which would otherwise be costly to the firm. However, these beneficial effects are confined to less-skilled women, as high-skilled women see their earnings decrease as they have a greater opportunity cost related to missed prospects of career advancements (Akgunduz and Plantenga, 2013; Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017). Likewise, Butikofer, Jensen and Salvanes (2018) show that the motherhood wage penalty is larger in high-earning and high-skilled professions with non-linear wage structures. Other factors that affect the magnitude of the motherhood wage penalty include prior wages before maternity leave was taken, especially in the UK, and the number of children (Waldfogel, 1998; Cukrowska-Torzewska and Matysiak, 2020). The literature illustrates that there is a negative wage penalty that exists due to maternity leave policies, which exacerbates the gender wage gap, but the magnitude of this effect is again dependent on individual characteristics and preferences.

3.4 Short-run vs Long-Run:

The effects of maternity leave policies on the labour market differ in the short- and long-run. Studies find that the labour market effects dissipate in the long-run (Girsberger et al., 2021; Stearns, 2018). Whilst Olivetti and Petrongolo (2017) show that maternity leave may have detrimental effects on labour market participation in the long-run if it induces women to stay out of work for extended or repeated periods and hinders them from re-entering on the same pre-maternity track. Although, Aisenbrey, Evertsson and Grunow (2009) argue that maternity leave policies affect the timing of re-entry rather than the type of re-entry. Ruhm (1998), using data from nine European countries, finds that short periods of paid entitlement, defined as less than 3 months, lead to a 3-4% rise in female employment rates with negligible effect on wages, but that longer entitlement, defined as greater than 9 months, has negligible impact on

employment but decreases hourly earnings by 3%. Similarly, Olivetti and Petrongolo (2017) show that female employment rises with job-protected parental leave up to 50 weeks and declines thereafter, and Del Rey, Kyriacou, and Silva (2021) find an inverted U-shaped relationship between maternity leave duration and female labour market participation. Another explanation for differing lengths of maternity leave and thus varying effects on mothers' labour market outcomes is a polarising effect, where career-orientated women who are highly educated delay childbirth and return to work after childbirth quicker once their maternity leave has expired (Gustafsson et al., 1996). These contrasting short- and long-run effects suggest there is an optimal leave length that minimises the negative impacts on labour market outcomes. Although studies show that making it easier to be a working mother may be more important to prospective mothers than the maternity leave length (Ruhm, 1998; Akgunduz and Plantenga, 2013; Olivetti and Petrongolo, 2017). Despite the widespread prevalence of maternity leave policies, the economic impact on mothers is not fully understood, and current research fails to capture the complexity of the matter concerning the motherhood wage penalty (Schonberg and Ludsteck, 2014; Arntz, Dlygosz and Wilke, 2017)

4.Data

4.1 The United Kingdom Household Longitudinal Survey (UKHLS)

Understanding Society (USoc) – the data set used for analysis – is a longitudinal household panel survey starting in 2009 and following 40,000 households in the UK. The survey contains individual- and household-level information, including income, employment, education and family decisions, as well as the views and perceptions surrounding them.

The large sample size and high quality of the data provide a diverse sample of respondents that are representative of the UK population. Particularly relevant to my analysis, the data contains information about whether the mother is currently on maternity leave and the start and end dates of the leave¹, meaning that the maternity leave length can be determined. Also, as the data is collected over multiple waves, this

¹ Due to a greater number of recorded start dates than end dates for maternity leave, interview date used as a proxy for maternity leave end date to preserve sample size.

enables the examination of the change and development of outcomes over time, which is paramount in this study to determine the wage effects of leave-taking.

4.2 Sample Selection

This paper uses data merged across waves, excluding observations obtained post-February 2020, due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. These observations will likely not be representative due to the extensive furlough scheme implemented in the UK and the altering of household dynamics, particularly those with children, as there was a shift towards working from home and childcare providers, and schools were shut for prolonged periods. As the focus is on the effect of taking maternity leave on women's labour income, male observations were excluded from the sample. Additionally, the sample restricts the age of participants to 18–55 years to prevent distortion of control variables and ensure valid comparisons between group. This is necessary because the age range is larger for those who have not taken leave, with 9% of participants older than 55, compared to the maximum age of 47 for those who have taken leave. The age range chosen acknowledges the minimum school leaving age of 16 in the UK, with a form of further education being undertaken until the age of 18, thus there will be no wage information recorded before this age. Moreover, the average age of a mother in the UK since the survey's commencement is 30 with the average age increasing to 33 for the fourth child; hence, this age range accommodates mothers who may have their last child in the first waves and aligns with the typical age range of mothers in the UK (ONS, 2023).

4.3 Summary Statistics

Table 1 presents the number of participants that were observed as being on maternity leave or not on maternity leave alongside the total number of participants by wave. The number of observations for participants currently on maternity leave is relatively constant over waves, ranging from 2–3% of the total observations per wave, excluding waves 1 and 10. This is due to the variable being recorded from wave 2 onwards; despite the possible caveat that some participants may have been on leave in wave 1, this allows observation of pre-leave variables. The reduction of observations in wave 10 is owed to the restriction of the sample to eliminate potential COVID-19 effects. The number of participants decreased from the first wave, indicating that response rates decreased; however, this did not result in any significant decrease in the observed number of

participants on maternity leave. Due to the use of the combined data over waves, the total sample size is 71,698 with a total of 1,594 observations of maternity leave.²

Table 1: Maternity Leave by Wave

Wave	Currently on Maternity Leave	Not on Maternity Leave	Number of Participants
1	0	9,375	9,375
2	264	8,310	8,574
3	232	7,984	8,216
4	215	7,701	7,916
5	189	7,533	7,722
6	206	7,410	7,616
7	156	6,817	6,973
8	135	6,192	6,327
9	135	5,774	5,909
10	62	3,008	3,070
Total Obs.	1,594	70,104	71,698

Source: University of Essex, Institute for Social and Economic Research. (2022). Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2020, 17th Edition, author's own calculations. Notes: Comparing women on leave to all women in the sample per wave. Column (2) provides the number of observed participants that are recorded as currently on maternity leave, and Column (3) provides those who are not. Column (4) provides the total number of participants per wave. 'Total Obs.' provides total observations for entire sample.

Table 2 presents summary statistics for all selected variables that will be included in subsequent regressions, split into the control group: women who have not taken maternity leave in the observed time, and the treatment group: women who have taken maternity leave. Although this is not an indication that the control group does not have children, as the average number of children for these participants is greater than zero, as shown in Table 2. Intuitively, this implies that the participants who have children in the control group have taken leave before the commencement of the survey and therefore have a greater number of older children on average than the participants who have been observed as having taken maternity leave. The inclusion of the older children variable allows this to be controlled for in subsequent regressions. The summary statistics (Table 2) indicate that participants who have taken maternity leave are on average 6 years younger, have a higher level of education, as shown by 43% of the sample obtaining a bachelor's degree compared to 36% of the sample who have not taken leave, and are 12% more likely on average to cohabit with their partner than

² Due to inconsistencies in the coded values of maternity leave variable after wave 5, the variable was recoded to preserve sample size.

participants who have not taken leave in the observed time. Counter-intuitively, wages on average are higher for participants who have taken leave compared to participants who have not taken leave in the sample by 3.9%. This could be explained by the greater proportion of the treatment group working in managerial roles, that are likely to have higher wages, or by the fact that there are 5% more young adults³ in the control group who are likely to earn less due to seniority and reduced time in the labour market. Furthermore, hours worked are greater for the treatment group by 1 hour per week on average, which would lead to higher wages. As expected, participants who have taken maternity leave are twice as likely to use childcare compared to participants who have not taken maternity leave, as they will have younger children that will not attend school.

Table 3 presents summary statistics for women who are kept in the analysis and those excluded due to sample selection or missing values. The unintended sample reduction was caused by missing and inapplicable responses for control variables. This is due to the nature of data collection, in which the same individuals are asked the same interview questions each wave but for outcomes that will not change over time, such as ethnicity or birthplace. This was minimised by carrying forward and/or backward observations per individual when response rates for these variables diminished. As shown in Table 3, participants excluded from the sample are on average 10 years older, worked 17 fewer hours per week, and earned 61% less per month. This is likely explained by the higher average age of excluded participants, some of whom will have retired and not earn a labour income. Moreover, excluded participants have fewer children and older children on average, which implies that although the issue of sample selection exists, it is likely that a higher proportion of non-mothers have been excluded from the sample than mothers. As a result, the number of observations of leave, which is already a small subset of the sample, is relatively preserved.

³ Defined as individuals aged 18-25.

Table 2: Summary Statistics for Sample

<i>Continuous Variables</i>	Not Taken Maternity Leave		Taken Maternity Leave	
	Average	Std. Dev	Average	Std. Dev
Age	38.23	10.71	32.03	5.27
No. of Children	0.68	0.96	1.60	0.91
Hours Worked	26.30	14.84	27.93	12.63
Wages	1,296.31	849.29	1,347.24	825.18
Prewage	1,303.06	848.57	1402.13	753.84
<i>Demographics</i>	Average (%)	Std.Dev	Average	Std.Dev
<i>Ethnicity</i>				
White	80.40	0.40	82.81	0.38
Black	6.04	0.21	4.64	0.21
Mixed	2.63	0.16	2.20	0.47
Asian	10.23	0.30	9.53	0.29
Other	0.70	0.08	0.82	0.09
<i>Education</i>				
<High School	6.67	0.25	3.19	0.18
High School	42.22	0.50	32.06	0.47
Bachelor	36.09	0.48	43.48	0.50
Higher	15.02	0.38	21.27	0.41
<i>Residency</i>				
England	84.11	0.37	84.32	0.36
Northern Ireland	4.37	0.20	5.08	0.22
Scotland	6.95	0.25	5.96	0.24
Wales	4.57	0.21	4.64	0.21
Rural	20.01	0.40	20.52	0.40
<i>Individual</i>				
UK Born	84.22	0.36	83.94	0.37
Cohabit	16.14	0.37	28.17	0.45
Health Condition	22.63	0.42	14.43	0.35
<i>Occupation</i>				
Routine	33.30	0.47	25.73	0.44
Intermediate	23.87	0.43	19.95	0.40
Management	42.83	0.50	54.32	0.50
<i>Mechanisms</i>	Average	Std.Dev	Average	Std.Dev
Older Children	0.28	0.60	0,10	0.36
Childcare	0.21	0.40	0.42	0.49

Source: University of Essex, Institute for Social and Economic Research. (2022). Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2020, 17th Edition, author's own calculations. Notes. Column (2) and (4) provide the average or percentages for women who have taken leave in the observed time frame and those who have not taken leave, respectively. Column (3) and (5) give standard deviation for women who have taken leave in the observed time frame and those who have not taken leave, respectively. Occupation type is split into three categories as defined by NS-SEC.

Table 3: Summary Statistics for Excluded Observations

<i>Continuous Variables</i>	In Sample		Excluded from Sample	
	Average	Std.Dev	Average	Std Dev
Age	38.09	10.66	48.64	18.55
No. of Children	0.70	0.97	0.45	0.87
Hours Worked	26.30	14.84	9.36	20.09
Wages	1,297.44	848.89	786.96	1015.42
Prewage	1,303.62	848.75	773.20	977.50
<i>Demographics</i>	Average (%)	Std. Dev	Average (%)	Std. Dev
<i>Ethnicity</i>				
White	80.45	0.40	71.92	0.45
Black	60.11	0.24	6.75	0.25
Mixed	2.62	0.16	2.55	0.16
Asian	10.21	0.30	16.89	0.37
Other	0.70	0.08	1.09	0.10
<i>Education</i>				
<High School	6.59	0.25	15.36	0.36
High School	42.00	0.49	38.50	0.49
Bachelor	36.25	0.48	46.02	0.46
Higher	15.16	0.36	11.72	0.32
<i>Residency</i>				
England	84.12	0.37	90.84	0.29
Northern Ireland	4.38	0.20	0.30	0.06
Scotland	6.92	0.25	5.39	0.26
Wales	4.57	0.21	3.45	0.18
Rural	20.51	0.40	19.42	0.40
<i>Individual</i>				
UK Born	84.22	0.36	78.93	0.41
Cohabit	16.41	0.37	10.15	0.30
Health Condition	22.45	0.42	33.40	0.47
<i>Occupation</i>				
Routine	33.13	0.47	15.55	0.36
Intermediate	23.78	0.43	12.16	0.33
Management	43.08	0.50	21.50	0.41
<i>Mechanisms</i>	Average	Std.dev	Average	Std.dev
Older Children	0.28	0.59	0.20	0.52
Childcare	0.21	0.41	0.08	0.27

Source: University of Essex, Institute for Social and Economic Research. (2022). Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2020, 17th Edition, author's own calculations. Notes. Column (2) and (4) provide the average or percentages for women who have taken leave in the observed time frame and those who have not taken leave respectively. Column (3) and (5) give standard deviation for women who have taken leave in the observed time frame and those who have not taken leave respectively. Occupation type is split into three categories as defined by NS-SEC.

5. Empirical Methodology:

5.1 OLS Regression:

To analyse a potential relationship between the maternity leave decision and the effect on wages, I estimate the following OLS regression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log(W_{i,t} + 1) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{MatLeave}_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Age}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Age}_{i,t}^2 + \sum_{k=4}^{k=7} \beta_k D_{\text{Ethnicity}_i} \\
 & + \sum_{k=8}^{k=10} \beta_k D_{\text{Education}_i} + \sum_{k=11}^{k=13} \beta_k D_{\text{Country}_i} + \beta_{14} \text{Rural}_{i,t} + \beta_{15} \text{UKBorn}_i \\
 & + \beta_{16} \text{Cohabit}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{Health}_{i,t} + \sum_{k=18}^{k=20} \beta_k D_{\text{Occupation}_i} + \sum_{k=21}^{k=29} \beta_k D_{\text{Wave}} \\
 & + \beta_{30} \text{OlderChildren}_{i,t} + \beta_{31} \log(\text{Prewage}_{i,t-1} + 1) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $W_{i,t}$ is monthly wage for an individual i at time t , $\text{MatLeave}_{i,t-1}$ equals 1 if individual i was on leave in the previous wave⁴, $t - 1$, and ε_{it} the error term. The dependent variable is monthly net labour income⁵ (monthly wages) in a log form to allow for percentage change interpretation as opposed to absolute change. This is more meaningful when comparing the effect across different levels of wages. The wage variable is adjusted by 1, such that observations are not lost when wages are 0 and the logarithmic transformation occurs.

Many observed characteristics affect both wages and the maternity leave-taking decision, which are explicitly included in the regression in the form of control variables to prevent omitted variable bias. These control variables are observed in the same time period as wages as the majority are pre-determined, and any variables which could vary whilst on maternity leave are recorded as ‘usual’ values, such that they do not need to be lagged by the length of leave taken. As shown in Equation 1, I control for age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and whether the participant has an older child because these are common determinants of wages and may also be correlated with the uptake of leave. The dummy variables specific to the subscript, denoted by ‘D’, are included as independent variables in the model, with the base groups being White, <Highschool, England, and Routine for Ethnicity, Education, Country, and Occupation

⁴ Data collected yearly thus each year corresponds to a wave and $t - 1$ corresponds to previous wave.

⁵ Sum of three earnings components: net usual pay, net self-employment income and net pay in second job (Fisher et Al, 2019).

respectively, which are dropped to avoid the dummy variable trap. I also include time dummies, D_{Wave} , to capture any changes over time, as wages are likely to fluctuate between waves due to inflation. By including a squared term for age, $Age_{i,t}^2$, heterogeneity in the relationship between age and wages across different age groups is captured, which improves the predictive power of the model. $Cohabit_{i,t}$ takes the value of 1 if a participant is living with a partner with whom it is assumed they share income and/or childcare. This is appropriate for this analysis, as Stearns (2018) shows that women in Great Britain are less likely to be married and tend to cohabit. $OlderChildren_{i,t}$ is a proxy variable for having already taken maternity leave, as it represents the number of children aged 10-15 that a participant has.

The coefficient of interest is β_1 . This captures the percentage effect of taking maternity leave on post-leave monthly wages.

5.2 OLS with Length of Leave Variable:

In the previous model, the maternity leave length is not considered, which ignores the fact that this length differs greatly in the UK due to wide variation in OMP. Therefore, including the length of leave will provide a more precise estimate of the relationship between maternity leave and wages. Furthermore, maternity leave length is pivotal to analysing the short- and long-run effects of leave-taking on wages. Equation 1 is adapted to observe the potential relationship between maternity leave length and the effect on wages using the below OLS regression:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log(W_{i,t} + 1) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 LengthLeave_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 Age_{i,t} + \beta_3 Age_{i,t}^2 + \sum_{k=4}^{k=7} \beta_k D_{Ethnicity_i} \\
 & + \sum_{k=8}^{k=10} \beta_k D_{Education_i} + \sum_{k=11}^{k=13} \beta_k D_{Country_i} + \beta_{14} Rural_{i,t} + \beta_{15} UKBorn_i \\
 & + \beta_{16} Cohabit_{i,t} + \beta_{17} Health_{i,t} + \sum_{k=18}^{k=20} \beta_k D_{Occupation_i} + \sum_{k=21}^{k=29} \beta_k D_{Wave} \\
 & + \beta_{30} OlderChildren_{i,t} + \beta_{31} \log(Prewage_{i,t-1} + 1) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)
 \end{aligned}$$

Where $LengthLeave_{i,t-1}$ represents the length of maternity leave taken by individual i in the previous wave, $t - 1$, in weeks, and all other elements are as in Equation 1. β_1 is the coefficient of interest and captures the percentage effect of taking an additional week of maternity leave on post-leave monthly wages.

5.3 Clustered Standard Errors:

I will use cluster-robust standard errors clustered by individuals to account for the serial correlation of individuals across waves. Such standard errors correct for this by allowing for arbitrary correlation and changing variances each cluster, providing more accurate estimates of statistical significance and confidence levels (Wooldridge, 2020).

5.4 Instrumental Variable Regression ⁶:

Taking maternity leave is not a decision in the UK, as mothers are legally obliged to take a minimum of 2 weeks (UK Government, 2022). However, the decision to have children and the timing of having children could be correlated with wages due to the opportunity cost of having children. This can result in missed opportunities for promotion, reduced working hours, and thus lower wages. Furthermore, the timing of having children can affect wages, as individuals may delay having children if they have greater education or career aspirations or until they are financially stable (Gustafsson et al., 1996). This can produce different wage effects for parents and non-parents for reasons not directly related to leave uptake. As there are many unobserved factors affecting both leave-taking and work circumstances, omitted variable bias can occur, leading to an underestimation of the effect of maternity leave on wages. Thus, the coefficient on length of leave might be biased due to endogeneity in the relationship between the maternity leave decision and wages. Therefore I rely on an instrumental variable (IV) approach to overcome this challenge.

Instruments for the leave-taking decision that have previously been used in the literature include birth orders, state policies, and firm-level policies (Waldfogel, 1997; Baker and Milligan, 2008; Chatterji and Markowitz, 2008). I will use the average length of leave within the 3 classifications of occupations, namely routine, intermediate, and management⁷ as the IV. The decision to take leave is likely influenced by social norms or workplace policies shared among co-workers rather than being solely driven by an individual's characteristics or preferences. Thus, the assumption that individuals within each group behave similarly is valid, and the use of information on someone else's leave decision as opposed to an individual's decision is possible. This suggests that this

⁶ Fixed effects regression not feasible as only 264 participants taken maternity leave more than once. (Appendix A1)

⁷ Classifications as defined by NS-SEC. Further differentiation between occupation is available but this reduces sample size per group.

instrument will be independent of wages, as it will capture the effect of the factors influencing the individual’s leave decision whilst being uncorrelated with the individual’s wage. Moreover, the IV should meet the relevance condition and will likely have a positive correlation with the maternity leave length, as the type of job you perform is expected to explain the variation in leave-taking behaviour. This is because occupations usually differ in terms of maternity leave benefits, job security and the nature of work performed which could all influence the leave-taking decision. Whilst the regression controls for characteristics shared between workers within the same occupation, such as education, there may be unmeasured factors that affect mothers’ decisions regarding maternity leave length, such as concerns about financial stability or whether the mother is the main earner in the household. This could lead to the IV being endogenous. Despite this, previous literature has used group behaviour as an instrument for individual behaviour, for example, Burke (2013) used the achievement of classmates as an IV for individual achievement suggesting that this is a valid instrument that is exogenous.

Table 4: Summary Statistics for Instrumental Variable

Occupation Type	Average Length of Leave	Std.dev	Number of Observations
Routine	29.64	3.50	364
Intermediate	29.52	3.53	350
Management	28.16	4.63	880

Source: University of Essex, Institute for Social and Economic Research. (2022). Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2020, 17th Edition, author’s own calculations. Notes: Column (1) shows the occupation type categories as defined by NS-SEC, Column (2) shows the average maternity leave length in weeks per occupation and Column (3) the standard deviation of these and Column (4) shows the total number of observations for those who have taken leave per occupation.

Table 4 shows the summary statistics for the instrument for participants who have taken periods of maternity leave, as the length of leave will be 0 for the control group. The average length of leave taken decreases the higher the rank of the occupation, with managerial roles having the lowest average length of maternity leave of 28.16 weeks. The number of observations varies between the groups but is sufficiently large, with 55.2% of mothers working in management, 22% in intermediate roles, and 22.8% in routine roles.

The first-stage IV regression equation is given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \widehat{LeaveLength}_{i,t-1} \\
&= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{AverageLeaveLength}_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Age}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Age}_{i,t}^2 \\
&+ \sum_{k=4}^{k=7} \beta_k D_{Ethnicity_i} + \sum_{k=8}^{k=10} \beta_k D_{Education_i} + \sum_{k=11}^{k=13} \beta_k D_{Country_i} + \beta_{14} \text{Rural}_{i,t} \\
&+ \beta_{15} \text{UKBorn}_i + \beta_{16} \text{Cohabit}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{Health}_{i,t} + \sum_{k=18}^{k=20} \beta_k D_{Occupation_i} \\
&+ \sum_{k=21}^{k=29} \beta_k D_{Wave} + \beta_{30} \text{OlderChildren}_{i,t} + \beta_{31} \log(\text{Prewage}_{i,t-1} + 1) \\
&+ \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3}
\end{aligned}$$

Where $\widehat{LeaveLength}_{i,t-1}$ is the fitted value of the endogenous variable $\text{LengthLeave}_{i,t-1}$, $\text{AverageLeaveLength}_{i,t-1}$ is the IV representing average maternity leave length in weeks within an occupation, and all other elements are as in Equation 1.

The second-stage IV regression equation is given below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\log(W_{i,t} + 1) &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \widehat{LeaveLength}_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 \text{Age}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{Age}_{i,t}^2 + \sum_{k=4}^{k=7} \beta_k D_{Ethnicity_i} \\
&+ \sum_{k=8}^{k=10} \beta_k D_{Education_i} + \sum_{k=11}^{k=13} \beta_k D_{Country_i} + \beta_{14} \text{Rural}_{i,t} + \beta_{15} \text{UKBorn}_i \\
&+ \beta_{16} \text{Cohabit}_{i,t} + \beta_{17} \text{Health}_{i,t} + \sum_{k=18}^{k=20} \beta_k D_{Occupation_i} + \sum_{k=21}^{k=29} \beta_k D_{Wave} \\
&+ \beta_{30} \text{OlderChildren}_{i,t} + \beta_{31} \log(\text{Prewage}_{i,t-1} + 1) + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

Where β_1 is the coefficient of interest capturing the percentage effect of maternity leave length on monthly wages post-leave, using the fitted values from Equation 3, and all other elements are as in Equation 1.

The results supporting the relevance and exogeneity of the instrument, along with the first- and second-stage IV regression results, are discussed in Section 6.3.

6.Results:

The literature review (Section 2) suggests that taking maternity leave reduces wages and accentuates gender inequality through the widening of the gender pay gap. Furthermore, it indicates that the motherhood wage penalty increases with the maternity

leave length, but the effects dissipate in the long-run. This section will discuss the OLS and IV regression results. The focus is on the variable of interest while highlighting further important results. Time trends are controlled for by including wave dummies, D_{Wave} , in all regressions.

Table 5: Effects on Wages (OLS and IV Results)

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Wages	Wages	Wages
	OLS	OLS	IV
Leave Taken	-0.158*** (0.0238)		
Leave Length		-0.002** (0.00061)	-0.003*** (0.000741)
Older Children	-0.055*** (0.00624)	-0.051*** (0.00625)	-0.052*** (0.00626)
Childcare	-0.032*** (0.00852)	-0.038*** (0.00867)	-0.038*** (0.00868)
High School	0.048*** (0.0149)	0.052*** (0.015)	0.052*** (0.015)
Bachelor	0.139*** (0.0159)	0.138*** (0.0161)	0.138*** (0.0161)
Higher	0.189*** (0.0175)	0.190*** (0.0177)	0.190*** (0.0177)
Constant	3.210*** (0.0824)	3.281*** (0.0896)	3.282*** (0.0895)
Observations	50,732	49,822	49,822
R-squared	0.368	0.359	0.359
Hausman Test		4.478**	

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.10. Each column is a separate regression with (1) and (2) presenting estimation results using OLS with the leave taken and leave length variable respectively. (3) presents estimation results using IV regression. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients are rounded to 3.d.p. Full regression results are provided in Appendices A2, A3 and A4 for each column respectively.

6.1 OLS with Leave Taken:

The predicted coefficients for the relevant variables are shown in Column (1) of Table 5, using the specification from Equation 1. The results indicate that the coefficient on leave taken, -0.158, is statistically significant at 1% and that taking maternity leave is

associated with a 15.8% reduction in mothers' monthly wages on average, having included a series of control variables such that the coefficient of interest is stable (Appendix A2). This suggests that there is a negative association between taking maternity leave and wages in the UK.

6.2 OLS with Length of Leave:

Column (2) of Table 5 shows the predicted coefficients for the relevant variables, using the specification from Equation 2. The coefficient of -0.002 on leave length is statistically significant at 5% and the results suggest that taking an additional week of maternity leave is associated with a 0.2% reduction in mothers' monthly wages on average, having included a series of control variables such that the coefficient of interest is stable (Appendix A3). Despite this effect being relatively small, when incorporating the average maternity leave length in the sample with the coefficient on leave length, taking 28 weeks of maternity leave is associated with a reduction of 5.6% in mothers' monthly wages on average. This is a reduced wage penalty compared to the 15.8% wage reduction found in Section 6.1 when leave taken was used, which suggests that the previous result overestimates the motherhood wage penalty. This may be partly caused by a reduced sample size, but it confirms that utilising the maternity leave length is crucial in the UK to accurately assess the relationship between maternity leave and wages and allows for focus on longer-term implications.

However, 52.4% of mothers in the sample take maternity leave greater than the average, with most taking 52 weeks in total, the maximum UK SML. Incorporating this with the coefficient on leave length, taking 52 weeks of maternity leave is associated with a wage reduction of 10.4% on average. This suggests that taking a longer maternity leave is associated with a greater wage reduction upon returning to work. This could imply that a shorter maternity leave would be preferred over a longer leave due to the negative wage penalty and that mothers will not be out of the labour market for prolonged periods. Yet, 25.7% of mothers in the sample take leave longer than 39 weeks. In the UK, SMP is paid for up to 39 weeks, so for leave taken in excess of this, no payment will be received from the UK Government. This might suggest that participants taking longer lengths of maternity leave receive additional benefits from OMP, and these in turn could induce mothers to remain out of work for long periods as found by Olivetti and Petrongolo (2017). However, taking longer maternity leave periods, could also be

explained by high childcare costs in the UK, with the average price of full-time childcare for a child under two at £285.31 per week (Jarvie et al., 2023). This may result in mothers preferring to take the maximum amount of maternity leave available, even if it is partially unpaid, to save on childcare expenditure.

As shown in Section 6.3, these OLS estimates are biased due to endogeneity in the relationship between the leave-taking decision and wages, and therefore these results do not convey the true causal relationship.

6.3 Instrumental Variable:

Table 6 shows the results of the first-stage regression, with the coefficient of 0.985 on the IV being statistically significant at 1%, validating the relevance of this instrument and showing that the average length of maternity leave within an occupation has a statistically significant positive correlation with the length of maternity leave as expected. In fact, average maternity leave length within an occupation explains about 80% of the variation in maternity leave length in the sample, as shown by the R-squared value. Additionally, the F-statistic of 157.6 is above the traditional threshold of 10 (Wooldridge, 2020), which reinforces the instrument’s strength. To test the validity of this instrument, the robust-adjusted Hausman test is run to determine whether the difference between the IV estimator and the OLS estimator is statistically significant, in which case OLS must be endogenous and the IV regression preferred. Table 5 shows that the test statistic of 4.478 is statistically significant at 5%, meaning the OLS and IV estimates are statistically significantly different, validating that the OLS estimate is biased and that the IV estimate should be used instead.

Table 6: First-Stage Results

(1)	
Leave Length	
Average Leave Length	0.985***

	(0.0148)
Older Children	-0.023*
	(0.0106)
Childcare	0.015
	(0.0221)
Constant	0.097
	(0.117)
Observations	49,822
R-squared	0.801
F-test	157.6

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. (1) presents first-stage regression results with leave length as the dependent variable. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients are rounded to 3.d.p. Full regression results are provided in Appendix A4. F-test is a test for weak instruments.

The predicted coefficients for the relevant variables are shown in Column (3) of Table 5, using the specification from Equation 4. The coefficient of -0.003 on leave length is statistically significant at 1% and the results show that taking an additional week of maternity leave reduces mothers' monthly wages by 0.3% on average, having included a series of control variables. This is consistent with Ruhm's (1998) findings that longer leave reduces earnings. Compared to the OLS estimate of -0.002, this is a larger motherhood wage penalty and shows that the OLS estimate is biased downwards by 33.33% compared to the true parameter value. This implies that the OLS regression suffers from endogeneity bias and that the IV regression provides a more accurate estimate of the causal effect due to the larger absolute value of the coefficient of interest, which has greater statistical significance. This underestimation of the effect using OLS was expected, as the causal relationship between maternity leave length and wages is likely to be influenced by unobserved factors that affect both the leave-taking decision and wages, such as earnings potential or attachment to the labour market. This will lead to a negative bias, which is reflected in these results. When incorporating the average maternity leave length taken by the sample, taking 28 weeks of leave reduces mothers' wages by 8.4% on average, which is a 2.8% larger motherhood penalty than observed using OLS. With most participants taking 52 weeks of leave, combining this with the

coefficient of leave length results in monthly wages decreasing by 15.6% on average when this leave length is taken, which is 5.2% more than the result found using OLS. This coincides with the 9 –18% wage penalty found by Gangl and Ziefel (2009). However, this result is lower than the wage penalty of 20% found in Britain by Waldfogel (1998). One reason for this observed difference could be the introduction of the National Living Wage in the UK in 2016, which increased wages for low-paid workers, including many part-time workers who are more likely to be mothers, leading to a reduction in the pay gap between mothers and non-mothers (UK Government, 2016). Overall, these results highlight that taking any length of maternity leave has a negative impact on mothers' wages upon their return-to-work post-leave in the UK and supports the notion that maternity leave accentuates gender inequality.

As presented in Column (3) of Table 5, the coefficient on older children of -0.052 is statistically significant at 1% and suggests that having an additional older child is associated with a 5.2% wage reduction on average and all else constant. This could indicate that taking maternity leave has long-run effects on wages that do not dissipate as suggested by Girsberger et al. (2021) because wages are still negatively affected 10 –15 years after leave has been taken. However, it is not necessarily taking maternity leave per se that creates this sustained wage reduction but could additionally be owed to indirect effects of having children, such as reduced hours or changes in career paths to more 'mother-friendly' occupations, as found by Gangl and Ziefle (2009). Furthermore, the empirical setup differs from Girsberger et al.'s (2021) as they incorporate the number of months since the birth of a mother's first child to assess the long-run effect of maternity leave on wages, whereas I control for having older children, suggesting that my specification may not be as robust.

As shown in Column (3) of Table 5, the coefficient on childcare of -0.038 is statistically significant at 1% and indicates that using childcare is associated with a 3.8% wage reduction on average and all else constant. Intuitively, this holds, as childcare is expensive in the UK, with the Government only subsidising it when a child is aged 3 – 4 (Jarvie et al., 2023), and therefore mothers may take longer maternity leave and choose to work less to look after their child, which will reduce wages. This supports Olivetti and Petrongolo's (2017) findings that childcare costs can be an important determinant of maternity leave length.

6.4 Robustness Checks:

6.4.1 Excluded variables:

The hours worked variable was excluded from the regression due to its high correlation with wages, potentially creating causality. Similarly, the number of children variable was excluded due to its high correlation with the older children variable, which could cause multicollinearity (Appendix A5).

To examine the robustness of the results, I ran a similar regression as specified in Equation 4, but first replaced older children with the number of children and then included hours worked. Column (2) of Table 7 shows that using the number of children instead of older children reduces the statistical significance of the coefficient on leave length from 1% to 10%, for the IV estimate. However, the magnitude of the change is relatively small, with the alternative estimate predicting a 0.2% wage reduction when an extra week of maternity leave is taken. Furthermore, the explanatory power of the model remains relatively unchanged, as the R-squared values are similar. This justifies using the older children variable instead of the number of children variable, as the former allows for interpretation of the longer-term effects of taking maternity leave.

When the hours worked variable is included, the coefficient on leave length decreases in statistical significance from 1% to 10% as shown in Column (3) of Table 7. Moreover, the wage reduction when taking an extra week of maternity leave decreases by 0.1% for the IV estimate. Intuitively, the more you work, the greater your wage will be, which explains the high correlation between these two variables and suggests causality. Thus, the inclusion of the hours worked variable would increase the coefficient of interest and create a positive bias. Therefore, excluding this variable is justified as it isolates the relationship between leave-taking and wages. In summary, the results are robust to these specification changes.

Table 7: Robustness Checks (IV Results)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Wages	Wages	Wages	Wages
Leave Length	-0.003***	-0.002*	-0.002*	-0.003***

	(0.000741)	(0.000739)	(0.00067)	(0.00079)
Older Children	-0.052***			
	(0.00626)		(0.00582)	(0.00626)
Childcare	-0.034***	-0.041***	0.016	-0.036***
	(0.00868)	(0.0105)	(0.0086)	(0.00867)
Number of Children		-0.081***		
		(0.00528)		
Hours Worked			0.019***	
			(0.000574)	
Leave Length*Wave 6				0.002
				(0.00148)
Constant	3.282***	3.121***	3.560***	3.292***
	(0.0895)	(0.0871)	(0.0854)	(0.0892)
Observations	49,822	49,822	49,822	49,822
R-squared	0.359	0.362	0.437	0.358

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Each column is a separate IV regression with (1) presenting results from Table 5 (3) for comparison purposes. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients are rounded to 3.d.p

6.4.2 Shared Parental Leave:

From 5th April 2015, Shared Parental Leave (SPL) was introduced in the UK, allowing parents to share up to 50 weeks of unpaid leave and up to 37 weeks of paid leave between themselves (UK Government, 2023). This could affect the maternity leave length if mothers decide to reduce their leave and instead share it with their partner, which could affect the coefficient of interest and potentially invalidate previous findings. To test this, an interaction term between the length of leave variable and the appropriate wave⁸ is included in the specification of Equation 4. The results in Column (4) of Table 7 show that the coefficient on the interaction term of 0.002 is insignificant, and the coefficient on length of leave, -0.003, is unchanged. This establishes that the behaviour of mothers did not differ when SPL was introduced, indicating that previous results are robust to this policy reform. This is likely owed to the very low uptake of this policy⁹, at less than 10% of eligible parents, with many fathers taking annual leave

⁸ Wave 6 which is 2016 as length of leave lagged so this would represent taking leave in 2015.

⁹ Cannot identify in data whether shared leave was taken, so have no SPL uptake statistics for this sample.

instead due to complex eligibility criteria and poor financial coverage (Birkett and Forbes, 2019).

The OLS results for the above robustness checks are shown in Appendices A6 and A7, with the same conclusions found for the introduction of SPL. For the excluded variables, the coefficient on leave taken did not differ in statistical significance with the alternative variables being included, but the same conclusions as above were found for the length of leave variable in the OLS regressions.

6.5 Heterogeneity Analysis:

An apparent limitation of the results is that the effect of maternity leave length on wages is likely to differ across different groups of individuals. As shown in Column (3) of Table 5, higher education is associated with higher wages, as wages are 19% higher on average for having obtained a higher degree and 13.8% higher on average for having obtained a bachelor’s degree compared to individuals with no high school education, all else equal. Cipollone, Patacchini, and Vallanti (2014) show that education is a differentiating factor in terms of responsiveness to family-orientated policies. This may be because less educated mothers will need to return to work quicker due to greater financial instability, resulting in shorter leave taken. Furthermore, higher-educated women may be more likely to have jobs that offer greater job security and more flexible work arrangements, leading to greater lengths of leave being taken. However, highly educated women may also have greater career aspirations, leading to them delaying having children, having fewer children, and returning to work quickly to minimise the impact on their career progression (Gustafsson et al., 1996). Therefore, I consider how the effects vary by the education level of the mother.

Table 8: Heterogenous Effects on Educational Attainment (IV Results)

(1)	(2)
Wages	Wages
<i>Tertiary Education</i>	<i>Non-Tertiary Education</i>

Leave Length	-0.002** (0.000878)	-0.004** (0.00133)
Older Children	-0.043*** (0.00857)	-0.06*** (0.00925)
Childcare	-0.040*** (0.0119)	-0.028* (0.0128)
Constant	3.551*** (0.135)	3.255*** (0.122)
Observations	26,753	23,069
R-squared	0.315	0.300

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Each column is a separate regression with Column (1) presenting IV results for sub-sample who have completed tertiary education and Column (2) for sub-sample who have not completed tertiary education. Tertiary education refers to individuals who have obtained at least a bachelor's degree or equivalent. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients are rounded to 3.d.p

Splitting the sample into those who have completed tertiary education (bachelor's degree or higher) and those who have not, I run the regression specified in Equation 4 on these sub-samples, excluding the education dummy variables as this creates collinearity, to evaluate any heterogeneous effects of obtained education level on the maternity leave decision. The first-stage regression results (Appendix A8) validate the instrument's relevance and strength, as the coefficients on the IV are statistically significant at 1% and the F-statistics are greater than the traditional threshold of 10 (Wooldridge, 2020) for both the tertiary education and non-tertiary education groups. As shown in Table 8, the coefficient on leave length is statistically significant at 5% for both sub-samples. Mothers with tertiary education experience a 0.2% average wage reduction per week of maternity leave taken on return to work, compared to mothers without tertiary education, who experience a 0.4% average wage reduction. Combining these coefficients with the average maternity leave length, this shows that completing tertiary education is associated with a motherhood wage penalty that is 5.6% lower on average than mothers who have not completed tertiary education, all else equal, when 28 weeks of leave is taken. Furthermore, when combining these coefficients with the most observed maternity leave length, this implies that the wage penalty for mothers with higher education is 10.4% lower on average than mothers with lower education,

all else equal, when 52 weeks of leave is taken. This differs from the findings of Butikofer, Jensen and Salvanes (2018) in which the motherhood wage penalty was larger in high-earning and high-skilled professionals in Norway. This could be due to OMP, where those who are highly educated may be in jobs that provide greater OMP, thus favouring the re-entry of highly educated mothers who have access to these additional benefits. Furthermore, the contrast in findings could be owed to the difference in specifications, as Butikofer, Jensen and Salvanes (2018) consider highly skilled and high-earning professionals, whereas I focus on highly educated individuals. Despite education being highly correlated with skill, it is less correlated with wages due to individuals working in differing sectors such as the public sector where wages may be lower. This implies that the interpretation of the findings is somewhat different, and both findings may be true.

The OLS results for the above heterogeneity analysis are shown in Appendix A9, with the same conclusions found for the leave taken variable, but no difference in the coefficient of interest between the tertiary and non-tertiary education groups for the leave length variable.

7. Conclusion:

The limited UK-focused research shows that maternity leave policies can have a significant effect on mothers' post-leave wages, but my results show that the maternity leave length is pivotal in the UK. First, I find a statistically significant negative effect of maternity leave length on wages which may have long term implications. The motherhood wage penalty increases the longer the leave taken, with a wage reduction of 0.3% on average for each additional week taken. Furthermore, taking the most common length of leave, 52 weeks, reduces mothers' monthly wages by 15.6% on average upon their return to work. This highlights that unequal pay is a consequence of having children, as found by Kleven (2019a), and validates the findings of previous studies concluding that maternity leave policies accentuate gender inequality in the UK (Waldfogel, 1998; Gangl and Ziefel, 2009). However, it is important to consider that although taking maternity leave can reduce wages for mothers who intend on re-entering the labour market, this time off may be beneficial for infants (Stearns 2015). Secondly, I find that having an additional child aged 10-15 is associated with a 5.2% average reduction in the mother's wage, all else constant. This could suggest that taking

maternity leave may have long-run wage effects in the UK, either directly or due to the indirect effects of having children such as reduced working hours or changes in career path which could subsequently have a negative impact on the mother's pension.

Furthermore, I find that education is an important factor in disentangling heterogeneities in the maternity leave-taking decision. Completing tertiary education is associated with a motherhood wage penalty that is on average 10.4% lower than when no tertiary education has been completed, assuming the most observed maternity leave length of 52 weeks is taken. This suggests that less educated mothers are more adversely affected by taking maternity leave in the UK.

Examining these results, if policymakers want to reduce the gender imbalance associated with maternity leave-taking, they should consider the potential trade-offs between time out of the labour market and the financial well-being of mothers. The Women's Budget Group (2018), find that the current UK SML is based on an out-of-date model that leads to women bearing the brunt of care penalties. Despite SPL introduced to address the issue of gender discrimination and inequality in parenting, my results show that this policy did not have a significant impact on mothers' maternity leave decision-making and thus did not reduce the motherhood wage penalty. The results found coincide with the current debate on the need for policy reform of UK maternity and paternity policies and suggest that a greater focus should be on the social normalisation of parental leave-taking by fathers and the availability of policies to all in society, which could help to reduce gender discrimination and is vital to ensure that mothers can remain and advance in the labour market (OECD, 2017). Furthermore, if these maternity leave policies create sustained wage losses and contribute to male bias in pensions as suggested by Perez (2019, p.78), policymakers should reconsider pension policies in the UK to prevent sustained gender gaps and feminised poverty.

This paper is not exhaustive. I consider the length of maternity leave as given, but many underlying factors are likely to impact the maternity leave length such as childcare availability and subsidies, and the quality of pre-delivery job match, which should be considered in greater depth. Moreover, the effects of the leave decision extend beyond wages, affecting career progression and hours worked, among other labour market outcomes, which necessitate further exploration. To gain a more accurate measurement of the long-run effect of maternity leave on wages in the UK, the time since the birth

of a mother's first child should be incorporated into the model. This will allow a more in-depth analysis of potential long-term impacts of taking maternity leave such as effects on a mother's pension. Further research is needed to determine the optimal maternity leave length that should be offered in the UK.

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9. Appendix:

A1: Number of Participants Taking Leave More than Once

Number of Times Taken Leave	Number of Observations	% of Sample
2	244	0.340
3	16	0.022
4	4	0.006
Total Observations	264	0.368

Source: University of Essex, Institute for Social and Economic Research. (2022). Understanding Society: Waves 1-10, 2009-2020, 17th Edition, author's own calculations. Notes: Column (2) shows number of participants who have taken the number of leave periods specified in Column (1). Column (3) shows the number of observations as a percentage of the entire sample.

A2: OLS Regression Results with Leave Taken

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Wages	Wages	Wages	Wages
Leave Taken	-0.114*** (0.0265)	-0.114*** (0.0265)	-0.113*** (0.0265)	-0.158*** (0.0238)
Age	0.060*** (0.00417)	0.059*** (0.00407)	0.060*** (0.00408)	0.021*** (0.00287)
Age^2	-0.001*** (0.0000546)	-0.001*** (0.0000546)	-0.001*** (0.0000548)	-0.001 (0.0000376)
Black	0.027 (0.0257)	0.011 (0.0261)	0.034 (0.0282)	0.048** (0.0159)
Mixed	0.057 (0.0390)	0.044 (0.0393)	0.055 (0.0394)	0.016 (0.0218)
Asian	-0.056** (0.02)	-0.071*** (0.0204)	-0.047* (0.0221)	-0.015 (0.0127)
Other	0.004 (0.0666)	-0.010 (0.0664)	0.021 (0.0670)	0.019 (0.0377)
High School	0.182*** (0.0245)	0.180*** (0.0247)	0.173*** (0.0249)	0.0483** (0.0149)
Bachelor	0.556*** (0.0252)	0.554*** (0.0253)	0.549*** (0.0254)	0.139*** (0.0159)
Higher	0.752*** (0.0275)	0.751*** (0.0276)	0.750*** (0.0277)	0.189*** (0.0175)
Northern Ireland		-0.053 (0.0296)	-0.052 (0.0296)	-0.028 (0.0159)
Scotland		-0.032 (0.0296)	-0.033 (0.0235)	-0.012 (0.129)
Wales		-0.040 (0.0261)	-0.040 (0.0261)	-0.002 (0.0144)
Rural		-0.036* (0.0159)	-0.037* (0.0159)	-0.010 (0.00848)
UK Born			0.051* (0.0203)	0.03 (0.0116)
Cohabit				0.003 (0.0116)
Health				0.013 (0.00852)
Management				-0.053*** (0.00831)
Intermediate				0.322*** (0.0107)
Older Children				-0.055*** (0.00624)
Childcare				-0.032*** (0.00852)
Prewage				0.457*** (0.0129)
Constant	5.328*** (0.0741)	5.355*** (0.0746)	5.293*** (0.0783)	3.206*** (0.0824)
Observations	50,732	50,732	50,732	50,732
R-squared	0.106	0.107	0.107	0.368

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$. Each column is a separate OLS regression with time dummies included but the coefficients not presented. (1) presents controls for personal characteristics, (2) adds area characteristics controls, (3) adds work-related controls and (4) is the final specification including all control variables. (4) is presented for coefficients of interest in Column (1) of Table 5. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.

A3: OLS Regression Results with Length of Leave

	(1) Wages	(2) Wages	(3) Wages	(4) Wages
Leave Length	-0.001* (0.00056)	-0.001* (0.00056)	-0.002** (0.00059)	-0.002** (0.000613)
Age	0.045*** (0.000426)	0.044*** (0.00426)	0.042*** (0.00415)	0.017*** (0.0029)
Age^2	-0.001*** (0.0000568)	-0.001*** (0.0000568)	-0.001*** (0.0000556)	-0.001 (0.0000381)
Black	0.028 (0.0257)	0.012 (0.0262)	0.033 (0.0269)	0.051** (0.016)
Mixed	0.063 (0.0396)	0.050 (0.0399)	0.045 (0.0404)	0.022 (0.0222)
Asian	-0.057** (0.02)	-0.070*** (0.0205)	-0.044* (0.0213)	-0.014 (0.0128)
Other	0.005 (0.0672)	-0.009 (0.0670)	0.039 (0.0627)	0.020 (0.0378)
High School	0.187*** (0.0247)	0.184*** (0.0248)	0.181*** (0.0244)	0.052*** (0.015)
Bachelor	0.552*** (0.0253)	0.550*** (0.0254)	0.542*** (0.0249)	0.138*** (0.0161)
Higher	0.750*** (0.0276)	0.749*** (0.0277)	0.751*** (0.0271)	0.190*** (0.0177)
Northern Ireland		-0.053 (0.03)	-0.047 (0.029)	-0.027 (0.0161)
Scotland		-0.034 (0.0238)	-0.032 (0.0234)	-0.012 (0.131)
Wales		-0.038 (0.0265)	-0.037 (0.026)	-0.002 (0.0145)
Rural		-0.034* (0.0161)	-0.039* (0.0157)	-0.008 (0.00857)
UK Born			0.049* (0.0198)	0.004 (0.0116)
Cohabit				0.009 (0.00857)
Health				-0.058*** (0.00838)
Management				0.321*** (0.0108)
Intermediate				0.020 (0.0109)
Older Children				-0.051*** (0.00625)
Childcare				-0.038*** (0.00867)
Prewage				0.456*** (0.0132)
Constant	5.616*** (0.0781)	5.355*** (0.0746)	5.631*** (0.0795)	3.283*** (0.096)
Observations	49,822	49,822	49,822	49,822
R-squared	0.094	0.0946	0.0909	0.359

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Each column is a separate OLS regression with time dummies included but the coefficients not presented. (1) presents controls for personal characteristics, (2) adds area characteristics controls, (3) adds work-related controls and (4) is the final specification including all control variables. (4) is presented for coefficients of interest in Column (2) of Table 5. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.

A4: First-Stage and IV Results

	(1) Leave Length	(2) Wages
Average Leave	0.985*** (0.0148)	
Leave Taken		-0.003*** (0.000741)
Age	0.009 (0.00515)	0.018*** (0.0029)
Age^2	-0.001 (0.0000645)	0.001*** (0.0000381)
Black	0.016 (0.0401)	0.051** (0.016)
Mixed	0.048 (0.0537)	0.021 (0.0222)
Asian	0.016 (0.036)	-0.014 (0.0128)
Other	0.058 (0.103)	0.020 (0.0379)
High School	-0.047 (0.0275)	0.052** (0.015)
Bachelor	-0.063* (0.0305)	0.138*** (0.0161)
Higher	0.015 (0.0381)	0.190*** (0.0177)
Northern Ireland	-0.006 (0.0464)	-0.027 (0.0161)
Scotland	-0.006 (0.0372)	-0.011 (0.131)
Wales	-0.016 (0.0458)	-0.002 (0.0145)
Rural	0.001 (0.0225)	-0.008 (0.00856)
UK Born	0.025 (0.0299)	0.004 (0.0116)
Cohabit	-0.016 (0.0288)	0.009 (0.0856)
Health	0.005 (0.0185)	-0.058*** (0.00837)
Management	0.036 (0.0216)	0.322*** (0.0108)
Intermediate	0.009 (0.022)	0.019 (0.0109)
Older Children	-0.023* (0.0106)	-0.052*** (0.00626)
Childcare	0.015 (0.0221)	-0.036*** (0.00868)
Prewage	-0.387*** (0.01)	0.456*** (0.0132)
Constant	0.097 (0.117)	3.282*** (0.0895)
Observations	49,822	49,822
R-squared	0.801	0.359

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Time dummies are included but the coefficients not presented. (1) presents the first-stage regression with leave length as the dependent variable. (2) presents the IV regression with wages as the dependent variable. (1) and (2) are presented for coefficients of interest in Table 6 and Column (3) of Table 5 respectively. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.

A5: Correlation Matrix

	Wages	Older Children
Hours Worked	0.713	
Number of Children		0.569

A6: Robustness Checks for OLS results with Leave Taken

	(1) Wages	(2) Wages	(3) Wages	(4) Wages
Leave Taken	-0.158*** (0.0238)	-0.124*** (0.0240)	-0.091*** (0.0216)	-0.165*** (0.0269)
Older Children	-0.055*** (0.00624)		-0.025*** (0.00581)	-0.055*** (0.00624)
Childcare	-0.032*** (0.00852)	0.045*** (0.0103)	0.019* (0.00846)	-0.032*** (0.00852)
Number of Children		-0.081*** (0.00529)		
Hours Worked			0.019*** (0.000568)	
Leave Taken*Wave 6				0.051 (0.0473)
Constant	3.21*** (0.0824)	3.056*** (0.0801)	3.539*** (0.0793)	3.206*** (0.0824)
Observations	50,732	50732	50732	50732
R-squared	0.368	0.372	0.447	0.368

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Each column is a separate OLS regression with (1) presenting results from Table 5 (1) for comparison purposes. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.

A7: Robustness Checks for OLS results with Leave Length

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Wages	Wages	Wages	Wages
Leave Length	-0.002** (0.00061)	-0.001 (0.000551)	-0.001* (0.000486)	-0.002** (0.000661)
Older Children	-0.051*** (0.00625)		-0.024*** (0.00581)	-0.051*** (0.00626)
Childcare	-0.038*** (0.00867)	0.040*** (0.0105)	0.015 (0.00856)	-0.038*** (0.00867)
Number of Children		-0.081*** (0.00528)		
Hours Worked			0.019*** (0.000573)	
Leave Length*Wave 6				0.001 (0.00137)
Constant	3.28*** (0.0896)	3.155*** (0.0869)	3.587*** (0.0851)	3.316*** (0.0893)
Observations	49,822	49,822	49,822	49,822
R-squared	0.359	0.362	0.437	0.358

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Each column is a separate OLS regression with (1) presenting results from Table 5 (2) for comparison purposes. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p

A8: First-Stage Results for Heterogenous Effects on Educational Attainment

	(1)	(2)
	Leave Length <i>Tertiary Education</i>	Leave Length <i>Non-Tertiary Education</i>
Average Leave Length	0.986*** (0.0187)	1.040*** (0.0572)
Older Children	-0.027* (0.0136)	0.013 (0.0455)
Childcare	0.008 (0.0269)	-0.115 (0.144)
Constant	-0.147 (0.194)	-0.013 (0.199)
Observations	26,753	23,069
R-squared	0.790	0.517
F-test	113.01	67.33

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Column (1) and Column (2) present first-stage regression results for tertiary education and non-tertiary education samples respectively, with leave length as the dependent variable. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. F-test is a test for weak instruments. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.

A9: Heterogenous Effects on Educational Attainment (OLS Results)

	(1) Wages <i>Tertiary Education</i>	(2) Wages <i>Non-Tertiary Education</i>	(3) Wages <i>Tertiary Education</i>	(4) Wages <i>Non-Tertiary Education</i>
Leave Taken	-0.148*** (0.0289)	-0.184*** (0.0426)		
Leave Length			-0.002** (0.000748)	-0.002* (0.000929)
Older Children	-0.045*** (0.00854)	-0.064*** (0.00925)	-0.043*** (0.00857)	-0.061*** (0.00857)
Childcare	-0.034** (0.0116)	-0.03 (0.0127)	-0.041*** (0.0118)	-0.031* (0.0129)
Constant	3.540*** (0.134)	3.156*** (0.108)	3.586*** (0.136)	3.257*** (0.122)
Observations	26919	23813	26,753	23,069
R-squared	0.316	0.315	0.315	0.300

Notes: Cluster-robust standard errors in parenthesis, where ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1. Each column is a separate regression with Column (1) and (3) representing OLS results for sub-sample who have completed tertiary education for the leave taken and leave length variable respectively and Column (2) and (4) for sub-sample who have not completed tertiary education for leave taken and leave length respectively. Tertiary education refers to individuals who have obtained at least a bachelor's degree or equivalent. Only coefficients relevant to analysis are included in table but controls include age, ethnicity, education, country of residence, type of area of residence, birth country, cohabiting, health, occupation type and time trends. Coefficients rounded to 3.d.p.